

HARMFUL ALGAE NEWS

An IOC Newsletter on toxic algae and algal blooms

<http://ioc.unesco.org/hab/news.htm>

No. 35

• HANA

First IOC/HANA Workshop on Harmful Algal Blooms in North Africa

It was in Casablanca, Morocco, that twenty four experts from Egypt, Tunisia, Algeria and Morocco met from 18 to 20 October 2007, together with their eight guests, to discuss HAB problems in the HANA region. "HANA", or Harmful Algae in North Africa, is the network initiated by twelve young scientists from North Africa while attending an IOC training course in Salammbô, Tunisia in 2003. HANA was endorsed by IOC in 2005 as one of its regional networks for HABs.

The workshop programme was conceived with more than one objective in mind. It consisted of reports and scientific presentations, invited lectures

and round tables.

The scientific presentations reflected the considerable work presently carried out by young and more advanced scientists on potentially harmful microalgae in the region. They also provide a picture of the state of the marine environment regarding these issues. This is particularly obvious where economically important bivalve resources are under threat, namely in Morocco and Tunisia, the only two countries of the region where an institutionalized monitoring programme is in place.

In Morocco, seven sites are monitored on both the Mediterranean

and Atlantic coasts of the country. Of the diverse potentially harmful species recorded, some are of more concern than others: *Alexandrium minutum* (Nador Lagoon, Mediterranean) causing PSP contamination, *Lingulodinium polyedrum* (Abda Doukkala, Atlantic) contaminating shellfish with DSP, and three *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. (coastal Atlantic waters). Work has begun on dinoflagellate cysts and their possible implication in outbreaks of toxic species in Walidia Lagoon.

In Tunisia, toxic blooms lead to heavy fish mortality in the Gulf of Gabes in 1995, inciting the authorities to launch

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Modified ichthyoviscometer shows high viscosity in *Chattonella* culture

Introduction

Striking amounts of mucus accompany some blooms of *Chattonella* spp. As *Hornellia marina*, *Chattonella marina* (Subramanyan) Hara et Chihara was first described in 1954 [1] from viscous, slimy blooms causing huge kills of wild fish. As *Hemientreptia antiqua*, *Chattonella antiqua* (Hada) Ono was first described in 1974 [2] from blooms in which an enormous number of young cultured yellowtail died from "disturbance of respiration by mucous films" or "respiratory injury by mucus". A well-developed glycocalyx invests *C. antiqua* cells (Fig. 1), with fine filaments apparently continuous through the plasma membrane. This glycocalyx is

Fig. 1. Light micrograph of *Chattonella antiqua* cell illustrating glycocalyx on the cell surface. Scale bar = 5 μ m; gc: glycocalyx.

microfibrillar, and rich in a neutral carbohydrate-protein complex and acidic complex carbohydrates [3], while *C. marina* glycocalyx shows immunologically mediated adhesion to fish gills [4]. More than any other phytoplankton, *Chattonella* cells also produce reactive oxygen species (ROS)

[5], associated with the cell surface, the glycocalyx or both [6-7]. This ROS, as well as its accompanying fatty acids are toxic to bacteria and, separately or in concert, may modulate allelopathic action against ambient bacteria [8]. Nevertheless, since 2000, the ROS

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The publication of Harmful Algae News is sponsored by the Spanish Institute of Oceanography, Vigo, and the Department of Biology, University of Copenhagen.

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a monitoring programme in shellfish areas. Most of the toxicity episodes in the last six years appear to have been due to *Karenia selliformis*, though *Alexandrium minutum*, *Coolia monotis*, *Karlodinium veneficum* and *Prorocentrum minimum* also occur. Investigation of epiphytic microalgae on *Posidonia oceanica* leaves is just beginning. Of practical importance are the attempts to assess the rate of detoxification in clams.

Algeria did not report any toxicity episodes although fifteen potentially harmful species occur. High biomass blooms of the dinoflagellate *Lepidodinium chlorophorum*, the diatom *Cyclotella meneghiniana* and the coccolithophore *Holococcolithophora sphaeroides* developed in Algiers harbour in 2003, and *Scrippsiella trochoidea* along the coast in 2006.

Phytoplankton investigations in Egypt began with the observations of recurrent red tides in the Eastern Harbour of Alexandria since 1960. The red tides were caused by the then newly described *Alexandrium minutum*. Although no formal monitoring programme is in place, the E. Harbour and neighbouring coastal embayments were continuously monitored for red tides and heavy blooms, although irregularly. Heavy fish kills accompanied the last bloom of *A. minutum* in 1994. Since then, *A. minutum* has become insignificant, replaced by other potentially harmful species such as *Chattonella* spp., *Prorocentrum triestinum*, *P. minimum*, and *Pseudo-*

nitzschia spp. In a new development, a survey of epiphytic microalgae along the coast revealed benthic blooms of *Ostreopsis* spp. and *Oscillatoria* spp.

A variety of issues were dealt with by the six invited lecturers: Phytoplankton Strategies (Tim Wyatt), the IOC-ICES-PICES HAEDAT data base (Monica Lion), Monitoring and Management of Phytoplankton and Phytotoxins (Catherine Belin), Biology, Ecology and Oceanography of *Dinophysis* spp. (Beatriz Reguera), Occurrence of Harmful Freshwater Cyanobacteria Blooms in North Africa (B.Oudra), and the proposed project for cooperation between HANA and DANIDA (Jacob Larsen).

Three round tables were held respectively at the end of each day. They were devoted to free discussions of research priorities (chair B. Reguera), monitoring and management priorities (chair C. Belin) and to HANA business (chair Y. Halim). The round tables agreed on a number of recommendations.

Recommendations of the workshop:

1. All countries of the region should launch monitoring and management programmes of phytoplankton, phytotoxins and the quality of the environment.
2. A training course on taxonomy of harmful algae and on monitoring should be held soon in the region.
3. Selected experts from the HANA region should be trained for toxin analysis at IFREMER, France.
4. Biotxin experts from the HANA region should be represented in the IPHAB Task Team on Biotxin

regulation.

5. A link to HAEDAT should be added to the HANA web site and HANA data be introduced to HAEDAT.

6. The HANA web site (<http://ioc.unesco.org/hab/HANA/hana.htm>) should be updated and completed regarding the directory, the list of publications and the list of species.

7. As no representatives from Mauritania and Libya were present, the organizers are urged to insure the participation of all countries of the region at the next meetings.

8. Presentations in French language must be accompanied by slides in English.

9. The second IOC/HANA workshop must be convened in 2009. The invitation of Egyptian participants to host the next workshop at the Department of Oceanography, Faculty of Science in Alexandria, Egypt, was accepted.

10. Extra budgetary funding should be sought to allow more participants from the region to attend the next workshop.

During the third round table, the participants elected the bureau of HANA for the next two years as follows:

HANA chair: Youssef Halim.

HANA Vice chair: Hamid Taleb.

National coordinators: Amany Ismael for Egypt, Hassina Illoul for Algeria, Asma Hamza for Tunisia and Chafik Abdelghany for Morocco.

At the end of the meeting the HANA community agreed unanimously that the workshop had been both successful and enjoyable.

Y. Halim, HANA Chairman. Univ. of Alexandria, Alexandria, Egypt.
Email: youssefhalim@hotmail.com.

Participants in the first HANA workshop.

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produced by *C. marina*, relatively large in amount though it is, has been shown [10-12] insufficient to kill fish. Since 2004, respiratory disturbance by mucus is again considered [11-12], as originally thought by Hada [2] for *C. antiqua*, to be a major factor in fish mortality, perhaps accompanied by a factor producing osmotic distress [9].

Perhaps confusingly, fish mucus [13] and bivalve-mollusc mucus [9] increase the secretion of ROS by *Chattonella*, so ROS production seems likely to be increased by passage through fish and bivalve gills. Whether this gill passage, with attendant exposure to fish and bivalve mucus, likewise cause *Chattonella* to secrete more of its own mucus appears not to have been reported.

In this preliminary study we measured rheological properties, during flow through fish gills, of cultures of five phytoplankton taxa, compared to that of culture medium. Of the taxa tested, several are known to produce mucus. *Heterosigma akashiwo* surrounds itself with a glycocalyx closely comparable with that of *C. antiqua* [20-21] while *Chaetoceros* sp. can provoke damage to and clogging of fish gills associated with production of mucus by the fish [22], and *Skeletonema costatum* uses mucus to regulate cell-cell aggregation [23]. Since in this study only cultures of *C. antiqua* showed increased viscosity, our discussion has centred on this species and its congener *C. marina* which shows comparable harmful effects.

Methods

Cultures of phytoplankton (Table 1) were grown in the ACRO laboratory at 23°C, in modified SWM-3 medium [24] under a light:dark regime of 12h:12h with

Table 1. Cultures used

Species	IVS model	Date	Growth phase	Concentration during trials (cells.mL ⁻¹)	Yield stress (Pa) ⁽¹⁾	Max notional cell volume (including gc) (µm ³) ⁽²⁾	Max notional volume fraction ⁽³⁾
Diatoms							
<i>Skeletonema costatum</i>	Mark 3	13/02/07	Log	403000	ns	3.4 x 10 ⁻⁴	1.4 x 10 ⁻²
	Mark 3	16/02/07	Log	652000	ns		2.2 x 10 ⁻²
<i>Chaetoceros</i> sp.	Mark 3	13/02/07	Log	220000	ns	1.0 x 10 ⁻³	2.2 x 10 ⁻⁴
	Mark 3	16/02/07	Stationary	242000	ns		2.4 x 10 ⁻⁴
<i>Thalassiosira minima</i>	Mark 3	12/02/07	Log	233000	ns	5.5 x 10 ⁻²	1.3 x 10 ⁻⁴
	Mark 3	16/02/07	Stationary	606000	ns		3.3 x 10 ⁻⁴
Rhaphidophytes							
<i>Heterosigma akashiwo</i>	Mark 3	10/02/07	Log	43950	ns	1.8 x 10 ⁻³	8.2 x 10 ⁻⁵
	Mark 3	11/02/07	Log	107500	ns		2.0 x 10 ⁻⁴
	Mark 3	15/02/07	Stationary	311000	ns		5.8 x 10 ⁻⁴
<i>Chattonella antiqua</i>	Mark 3	11/02/07	Log	1600	ns	7.0 x 10 ⁻⁵	1.1 x 10 ⁻³
	Mark 3	14/02/07	Log	6050	ns		4.2 x 10 ⁻³
	Mark 3	16/02/07	Log	5300	ns		3.7 x 10 ⁻³
	Mark 3	17/02/07	Stationary	19500	9*		1.4 x 10 ⁻²
	Mark 2	19/01/07	Old culture	nd	17**		nd

(1) 1 Pa ~0.01 cm water. (2) Cell volumes calculated from largest cell dimensions found in literature, including glycocalyx when present. (3) Not including volume partly enclosed by setae of *Chaetoceros* sp. * $P < 0.1$, $n = 4$; ** $P < 0.05$, $n = 3$.

“daylight” fluorescent illumination at 300 µmol photons·m⁻²·s⁻¹.

Rheological (mechanical) properties of seawater and cultures were measured at the scales of flow through the gills of freshly killed juvenile (14 to 15 cm) Faria brown trout (*Salmo trutta*). The fish were kept starved in lake water for several days, and killed by cardiac puncture immediately before use. The genus *Salmo* is euryhaline.

Measurements used the Mark 2 ichthyoviscometer (IVM) [25], or the purpose-developed Mark 3 IVM (Fig. 2). The latter uses much smaller volumes of test medium than the Mark 2 (20 ml per measurement, for a hydrodynamic pressure P sweep of 300 to 0 Pa). It consists of a shortened measuring cylinder (MC) (internal and external diameters 2.9 cm and 3.2 cm respectively) standing in an aquarium (internal dimensions 42.9 x 18.6 cm) containing 6-7 cm of water. The pressure probe and recording

components in Mark 3 were the same as in the Mark 2. As there was sometimes drift in the pressure sensor set-up over several minutes, the time scale of a single measurement, we added another new feature, a yield-stress tube (YST). This is a flexible tube with a tap, joining the contents of the cylinder with the contents of the aquarium. During measurements this tap was kept closed, then after completion of each measurement the tube was opened. Because of scale dependence in yield stress Y of the EPS (see Box 2), even when Y was positive in the gills of the fish, it was negligible in the YST (confirmed by visual observation of the water level in the cylinder relative to that in the aquarium). The YST was used to check for any effect of instrument drift on recorded Y .

Each IVM has a characteristic value of J , the volume flow through the fish for every 1 Pa change in hydrostatic pressure. For the Mark 2, J was 3.14 x 10⁻⁶ m³ Pa⁻¹ [25], but J in the Mark 3 was only about one fiftieth of this, 6.66 x 10⁻⁸ m³ Pa⁻¹. Less test material flows through the fish gills in the Mark 3 IVM, so any tendency the test material might have to clog or concentrate during flow should be less marked in the Mark 3 set-up than in the Mark 2. This tendency may have been slightly offset by the smaller fish we used, ~15 g compared with ~25 g used previously [25].

Fig. 2. Sketch of the Mark 3 ichthyoviscometer (not to scale).

Box 1

We use the term *ichthyoviscometry* to mean the measurement of the viscosity of ventilating water as it passes over and between fish gills. Dissolved, colloidal or suspended material may increase the viscosity of this water to the extent that a fish may have to consume more oxygen to fuel the energy needed to pump the water over its gills than it can extract from the water pumped, and it would then suffocate through oxygen lack [14]. Such polymeric material may give the water a viscosity that depends on the deformation type and rate D [18]. One possible manifestation of D -dependent viscosity is a yield stress Y (a resisting pressure which must be overcome before material yields and flows) higher than the head pressure a fish can develop across its gills. In this case ventilation will be impossible and the fish will likewise suffocate [25]. *Ichthyoviscometry* can be carried out using an *ichthyoviscometer* (Fig. 2).

Results

Table 1 shows the results of trials with cultures of three diatom and two raphidophyte species. Even concentrated cultures, whether in logarithmic or stationary phases, of *Skeletonema costatum*, *Chaetoceros*

Box 2

It has been suggested that viscosity in blooms of the dinoflagellate *Karenia mikimotoi* could kill fish by increasing the energy needed to ventilate their gills, to the extent that the oxygen extracted from the seawater would then be insufficient to fuel this energy [14]. Results obtained using an ichthyoviscometer supported this hypothesis [15] in a study showing that polymeric thickening alone could have killed the fish, but that haemolytic ROS were also produced, which may have significantly contributed.

Since phytoplankton-derived organic matter to some extent produces flocculates [16] and also heterogeneous distribution of viscosity at scales ≤ 1 cm [17], its mechanical properties are likely a function of the flow regimes (shearing, elongational, etc.) [18] and scales of the system constraining the flow [19]. The most relevant flow regimes and scales, however, are hard to identify and characterise in each case, but the aim of an ichthyoviscometer, using the flow-ways between fish gills as the measuring system, is to get the flow regimes and the scales right for measuring rheological thickening during flow in fish gills.

sp., *Thalassiosira minima* and the often ichthyotoxic *Heterosigma akashiwo* showed no statistically discernible yield stress Y . For *Chattonella antiqua*, however, although log-phase cultures of 1600 to 5300 cells mL⁻¹ showed Y not significantly different from water, a stationary-phase culture of 19,500 cells·L⁻¹ and an old culture in decline-phase showed values of Y of 9 and 17 Pa respectively (0.9 and 1.7 mm water).

Discussion

A culture of *Chattonella antiqua* with a cell concentration of 20,000 cells mL⁻¹ produced a yield stress Y of 9 Pa in the gills of trout, while an old culture in decline produced 17 Pa. Such values of Y are about an order of magnitude higher than those theoretically needed to prevent ventilation and thus suffocate young fish, which produce a maximum head pressure of only 0.6 to 1.5 Pa [26]. If blooms of *Chattonella antiqua* in the field produce similar values of Y , these blooms would easily kill captive fish by preventing gill ventilation. Volume fractions of cells with glycocalyxes (estimated conservatively high) in these cultures did not exceed ~2%, while it requires over 10% of suspended spheroids to significantly increase viscosity [19]. Therefore it is likely that diffuse colloidal EPS, rather than the volume of cells and glycocalyxes, was at least a major contributor in stopping flow of *Chattonella* culture through the fish gills. In *Chattonella*-associated fish kills, toxins, ROS, oxygen levels, biopolymeric structures [27], the role of heterogeneous viscosity (Box 2), flocculation in the high-shear flow between the gills, adhesion or slipping at the gill surface, and fish behaviour might all modify the roles of EPS-

modulated yield stress and viscosity increase. These subjects should thus be investigated together in *Chattonella* blooms to promote better understanding of fish mortality with a view to mitigation.

Acknowledgements

We thank G. Claireaux (CNRS - Station méditerranéenne de l'Environnement littoral, Sète, France) for kind help and loan of recording equipment, G. Guillou and Y. Descatoire (both of CNRS-CRELA, L'Houmeau, France), for technical advice and help with drawing Fig. 2, respectively. JM Faurs' fish farm, 19120 Altillac, France provided the trout.

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I.R. Jenkinson, Agency for Consultation and Research in Oceanography (ACRO), 19320 La

Roche Canillac, France.
Email: ian.jenkinson@wanadoo.fr.

T. Shikata & T. Honjo, Laboratory of Marine Environmental Science, Division of Bioresource and Bioenvironmental Science, Kyushu University, Hakozaki, Fukuoka 812-8581, Japan.

• France

Identification of *Pseudo-nitzschia multistriata* and *P. subpacificica* from French waters. Were they part of the cryptic flora?

Fig. 1. Map of France showing localities where *P. multistriata* (▼) and *P. subpacificica* (●) have been detected.

Identification of *Pseudo-nitzschia multistriata* (Takano) Takano and *P. subpacificica* (Hasle) Hasle have recently been confirmed with help of scanning electron microscopy (SEM). However, they were previously detected in French waters; the former appeared in 2002 and the latter in 2004, but their identification required further examination for confirmation.

P. multistriata was mostly observed in the autumnal phytoplankton of the Channel and Atlantic Ocean while *P. subpacificica* was mainly detected in the Atlantic during summer (Table 1, Fig. 1).

P. multistriata: First observed with light microscopy (LM), *P. multistriata* was characterized by short chains and sigmoid valve ends in girdle view (Fig. 2A) [1]. The apical axis of cells was 50-75 μm long and the transapical axis 2.9-3.7 μm wide ($n=24$). Cell overlap in chains was 9-13% of the length. When

observed with SEM, valves did not possess a central nodule and fibulae, and interstriae numbered 23-26 and 37-42 in 10 μm , respectively (Fig. 3). The interstriae were parallel or oblique (Fig. 3B) to the transapical axis and the striae contained two rows of poroids. The number of poroids per 1 μm (10-11) was close to the range described for strains from Italy (11-13) [2] and Morocco (11-12) [3]. However, it was the single parameter which differed from the original description where only 5 to 6 poroids in 1 μm were mentioned for this species [4].

P. subpacificica: First observed with LM, its asymmetrical valves drew attention (Fig. 2B). The apical axis of cells was 47-79 μm long and the transapical axis 4-6.3 μm wide ($n=32$). Chains had a cell overlap of 12-20% of the length. Occasional surface net samples were collected for SEM examination. A large central interspace was clearly visible (Fig. 4B) and the number of fibulae and interstriae was 14-20 and 28-30 in 10 μm , respectively. The biseriate striae contained 8 to 10 poroids in 1 μm , which is in agreement with other descriptions of this species [3, 5-7]. Molecular analysis of the internal transcription spacer (ITS) sequences was made on cultured material, and results

compared with known sequences of *Pseudo-nitzschia* species available in databases. In the absence of data equivalent to *P. subpacificica*, they were identical (100% identity) with three records of *P. cf. subpacificica* of which two sequences were from Spanish strains and the third from a Portuguese strain [8].

Owing to the distinctive shape of *P. multistriata* in girdle view, it would have been difficult to overlook this species during more than 20 years of

Fig. 2. Light micrographs of *Pseudo-nitzschia multistriata* and *P. subpacificica*. (A) Chain of *P. multistriata* in girdle view. (B) Chain of *P. subpacificica* in valve view. Scale bars = 20 μm .

Table 1. Monthly observations of *P. multistriata* and *P. subpacificica*.

	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D
<i>P. multistriata</i>								X	X	X	X	X
<i>P. subpacificica</i>						X	X	X	X	X	X	

Fig. 3. Scanning electron micrographs of *Pseudo-nitzschia multistriata*. (A) Valve outline. (B) Part of valves showing two different patterns of interstriae. (C) Tip of valve. Scale bars = 10 μm (A) and 1 μm (B, C).

Fig. 4. Scanning electron micrographs of *Pseudo-nitzschia subpacificica*. (A) Whole valve. (B) Central part of valve showing central nodule (arrow). (C) Tip of valve. Scale bars = 10 μm (A) and 1 μm (B, C).

phytoplankton monitoring. Thus, we can reasonably consider that it was not present earlier. In contrast, in spite of its asymmetrical shape in valve view, *P. subpacificica* could have been confused in light microscopy with *P. fraudulenta* with which it co-occurs.

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E. Nezan & N. Chomerat, Ifremer, 13 rue de Kérose, 29187 Concarneau Cedex, France.
Email: enezan@ifremer.fr

M.P. Crassous & E. Antoine, Ifremer, BP 70, 29280 Plouzané, France.

• Greece

The coincidence of an *Arthrospira* - *Anabaenopsis* bloom and the mass mortality of birds in Lake Koronia

An extremely dense bloom of the cyanobacteria *Arthrospira fusiformis* (Voronichin) Komárek et Lund and *Anabaenopsis arnoldii* Aptekarj (Fig. 1) occurred on 17 September 2007 in the shallow Lake Koronia. This is the first report of an *Arthrospira* bloom in Greek freshwaters. Cyanobacterial blooms however are common in eutrophic freshwaters in Greece [1-2]. Another dense bloom of the haptophyte *Prymnesium parvum* N. Carter coincided with a mass kill of birds and fish in Lake Koronia three years ago (September 2004) [3].

Lake Koronia (40° 40' 58" N, 23° 09' 33" E, altitude: 75 m a.s.l.) is located in N. Greece and over the past 20 years has undergone a dramatic decrease in water volume, surface area and depth due to anthropogenic activities. During this period the lake water became

brackish and in the summer of 2002 the lake dried up completely. After increased rainfall in 2003, water reaccumulated in the lake and in 2004 the water level had a maximum depth of 1 m. In 2007 the prolonged dry and warm period resulted in a maximum depth of just 0.5 m.

Arthrospira fusiformis population density was extremely high with 23 x 10⁶ filaments L⁻¹ (2.99 x 10⁹ cells L⁻¹, or 487.37 mg L⁻¹ w/w) close to the highest values reported from African lakes [4-5]. At the same time, *Anabaenopsis arnoldii* exhibited high population density as well (0.12 x 10⁹ cells L⁻¹). Euglenophytes were also present in the lake's phytoplankton. Zooplankton consisted only of individuals of the *Brachionus plicatilis* group complex that were present in low numbers.

A mass mortality of water birds was

observed to coincide with the *Arthrospira*-*Anabaenopsis* bloom preceded in June by a heavy *Microcystis aeruginosa* (Kützing) Kützing bloom (5.6 x 10⁹ cells L⁻¹) with its epiphyte *Pseudanabaena mucicola* (Naumann et Huber-Pestalozzi) Schwabe (12.4 x 10⁹ cells L⁻¹). The number of dead birds reported by the Hellenic Ornithological Society at the meeting organised by the Prefecture of Thessaloniki was estimated to be two hundred, including mostly flamingos *Phoenicopterus ruber* Linnaeus.

From the literature, it is known that mass mortalities of Lesser flamingos *Phoeniconaias minor* (Geoffroy) can be caused by the toxic *Arthrospira fusiformis* and *Anabaenopsis* species [4-6]. Ballot *et al.* [4] found that *A. fusiformis* strains produce

Fig. 1. Light micrograph of phytoplankton collected from Lake Koronia on 17 September, 2007. (A) Phytoplankton dominated by *Arthrospira fusiformis*. Scale Bar: 50 μm . (B) Filaments of *A. fusiformis* and *Anabaenopsis arnoldii*. Scale Bar: 20 μm .

microcystin-YR and anatoxin-a. Lanaras and Cook [7] first raised the possibility that *Anabaenopsis* species produce microcystins, reporting microcystin in a cyanobacterial bloom dominated by *Anabaenopsis milleri* Woronichin in a Greek water body. In 2001, the mass mortality of flamingos *Phoenicopterus ruber* and other water birds in southwest Spain was attributed to microcystins produced by toxic cyanobacteria (*Microcystis*,

Anabaena) [8].

The bird mortality in Lake Koronia during September 2007 was most likely caused by the heavy bloom of toxic cyanobacteria in the lake. The mass development of *Arthrospira*, *Anabaenopsis*, *Anabaena* and *Microcystis* species in the lake the last three years presents a health risk for wildlife and especially for water birds, and underlines the need for cyanobacteria and cyanotoxins risk

assessment and management. This is of great importance considering that Lake Koronia is covered by the Directives 79/409/EEC [9] and 92/43/EEC [10], the RAMSAR Convention (<http://www.ramsar.org>) and is part of a National Wetland Park [11].

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M. Moustaka-Gouni,
E. Michaloudi, M. Katsiapi &
S. Genitsaris, School of Biology,
Aristotle University of Thessaloniki,
GR-541 24 Thessaloniki, Greece.
Email: mmustaka@bio.auth.gr;
tholi@bio.auth.gr

• Tunisia

First bloom of dinoflagellate *Alexandrium catenella* in Bizerte Lagoon (northern Tunisia)

Bizerte Lagoon is located in northern Tunisia (37° 8' - 37°14' N, 9°46' -9°56' E). The surface area is about 128 km², maximum width 11 km, and maximum length 13 km; the mean depth is 7 m. The lagoon is connected to the sea via a canal 6 km long, as well as to Ichkeul Lake to the east via the 5 km long oued (= river) of Tinja (Fig. 1). In Tunisia, mussel and oyster farming are developed only in this lagoon.

In the context of the national surveillance network of bivalve production in northern Tunisia, two zones of clam production and five oyster and mussel farms are considered by the phytoplankton and phycotoxin surveillance programme for various products from the lagoon.

Fig. 1. Location of the sampling stations at the Bizerte lagoon.

Fig. 2. Microphotographs of *A. catenella* from Bizerte Lagoon, Nov 2007. a. General morphology; b. Hypotheca (sp: posterior sulcal plate).

Fig. 3. Rainfall recorded in the Bizerte region during 2007.

For the first time, in November 2007, a bloom of *Alexandrium catenella* was recorded in Bizerte Lagoon (Fig. 2). These proliferations affected especially the sampling sites located on the southern shore of the lagoon (MAT, FMB and SMN). This shore receives several fresh water inputs from the oueds. Moreover, precipitation recorded in the region of

Bizerte was more important from October to November 2007. Quantities of daily recorded rain reached approximately 55 mm (Fig. 3).

In the lagoon, *A. catenella* appeared for the first time at the end of the year 2006, between 27 November and 18 December. The densities recorded varied from 100 to 450 cells L^{-1} . During the same period in 2007,

Fig. 4. *A. catenella* numbers in Bizerte Lagoon, 2006-2007.

much higher concentrations have been observed (20×10^4 cells L^{-1}) (Fig. 4). During the 10 years of phytoplankton and phycotoxin surveillance in the area of bivalve molluscs production in Tunisia, mussel contamination by paralytic toxins was recorded for the first time, with concentrations higher than the threshold ($80 \mu g/100$ g of flesh) accepted by public health authorities. Values recorded by the Pasteur Institute of Tunis using the mouse bioassay [1] were between 140 and 330 $\mu g/100$ g of mussel flesh.

The national surveillance network for bivalve production detected *Alexandrium catenella*, for the first time, in the canal of Tunis in August 1997 [2]. During November 2007, we also recorded high concentrations of *A. catenella*, about 15.3×10^4 cells L^{-1} , in the navigation channel of Tunis.

In the Mediterranean Sea, *A. catenella* first appeared in 1983 along the Catalan coast (Spain).[3]. Its distribution area spread along the northwest Mediterranean coast with recurrent blooms in the 1996-1999 period in Barcelona harbour. These blooms were associated with paralytic toxin production [4]. In the Italian waters, *A. catenella* was also observed for the first time in 1999 in the Tyrrhenian Sea (Sardinia).

Toxic events due to the presence of gonyautoxins and saxitoxins have been observed in Thau Lagoon (southern France). Their origin is likely to be *A. tamarense* with suspicions from *A. catenella* [5-7]. Thau Lagoon shares some hydrobiological features with that of Bizerte. The periods when *A. catenella* appeared were the same in both ecosystems. In Thau, a new *Alexandrium catenella/tamarense*

event was observed during the year 2001; this one was more important than those in 1999 and 2000. From its consequences, it is comparable to the 1998 crisis. All the shellfish produced in Thau Lagoon (mussels, clams and oysters) reached for the first time the statutory toxicity threshold (80 µg eq. STX /100 g of flesh); toxicity was higher in mussels and clams (close to 500 µg eq. STX /100 g of flesh) than in oysters (about 160 µg eq. STX /100 g of flesh). In Italian waters, *A. catenella* was also

reported for the first time in 1999 in Sardinia [8].

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S. Turki & N. Balti, Institut National des Sciences et Technologies de la Mer, 2016 La Goulette, Tunisia.
Email: Souad.turki@instm.rnr.tn.

H. Ben Jannet, Direction Générale des Services Vétérinaires, Ministère de l'Agriculture et des Ressources Hydrauliques, 30 rue Alain Savary, 1002 Tunis, Tunisia.

• Tunisia

First detection of *Kryptoperidinium foliaceum* (Stein 1883) in Tunisian waters

Fig 1. Chart of Ghar el Melh Lagoon showing sampling stations

Fish mortalities were observed during the first fortnight of June in the lagoon of Ghar El Melh «Lac de Porto Farina» in northern Tunisia (Fig. 1). The lagoon has an area of about 3000 ha, and is considered euhaline on account of the diversity of environments which range from limnetic to hypersaline [1]. Climatic factors play a primary role in control of the physico-chemical parameters of this lagoon due to its shallowness, with a maximum depth of 1.5 m. During June, air temperature ranges from 16.4°C to 27.7°C, and mean rainfall is estimated at 10 mm in the region of Bizerte.

The diversity of the benthic vegetation in this lagoon has varied over time; the dominant plants were *Cymodocea nodosa* and *Zostera* in the 1970s, *Caulerpa prolifera* and *Zostera* in the 1980s, and these are now being

replaced by *Ruppia cirrhosa* and *Cladophora* [2]. Among the potentially toxic microalgae recorded in Ghar El Melh Lagoon are *Alexandrium minutum* with densities of the order of 2×10^5 cells L⁻¹ in June 1966 [3], and *Prorocentrum lima* with concentrations higher than 1.5×10^4 cells L⁻¹ in December 1966 [4].

Sampling carried out on 14 June 2007 at 3 stations led to the first detection, in Tunisian coastal waters, of the dinoflagellate *Kryptoperidinium foliaceum* (Figs. 2-7), in

concentrations higher than 10^5 cells L⁻¹. This species was previously reported in Mediterranean waters [5]. Samples collected at the rainfall-drainage channel (St 3) had a light brown colour due to high concentrations of *K. foliaceum* (1.8×10^5 cells L⁻¹) and of the cyanobacteria *Anabaena* (1.2×10^5 cells L⁻¹). The latter is frequently found in freshwaters but can withstand salinities up to 40 psu (Table 1). Concentrations of *K. foliaceum* showed a sharp decline from the peripheral stations towards the central parts of the lagoon. Therefore, stations 1 and 2 are the main bloom sites.

Kryptoperidinium foliaceum cells are spherical with a lateral compression (Figs. 2-4). Their size ranges from 29.3 to 52.0 µm. The thecae are very fragile, which renders observation of plates difficult (Figs 5-7). *K. foliaceum* is mainly found in brackish waters (down to 10 psu). Brownish waters of this species have been observed in different

Table 1. Physico-chemical parameters and phytoplankton concentrations in Ghar El Melh Lagoon (14 June 2007)

Parameter	St 1	St 2	St 3
Water temperature (°C)	27.3	27	29.5
Salinity (‰)	38.9	44	41
pH	8.53	8.71	8.22
Dissolved oxygen (mg/l)	5.14	3.8	5.47
Phytoplankton, cells/l			
<i>Kryptoperidinium foliaceum</i>	9.8×10^3	1800	1.83×10^5
<i>Scrippsiella subsalsa</i>	0	3400	0
<i>Prorocentrum micans</i>	700	1300	3100
<i>Anabaena</i> sp	1.1×10^4	0	1.22×10^5

Figs. 2-7. Microphotographs of *K. foliaceum* from Ghar El Melh Lagoon. 2: cells of *K. foliaceum* and *Anabaena* sp.; 3: *K. foliaceum* cell; 4: longitudinally flattened cell of *K. foliaceum*; 5: theca (ventral view); 6: apical plates 1' and 2'; 7: intermediary apical plates 1a and 2a.

parts of the Atlantic coast in summer between 1986 and 1988, and in spring 1991 following heavy rainfall [7]. It is not a toxic species, but mass mortalities due to anoxia have been reported with high concentrations ($>10^7$ cells L^{-1}). Dense blooms of *K. foliaceum* ($3.5 \cdot 10^8$ cells L^{-1}) were also reported in spring 1998 in South Carolina estuaries (USA) [6]. *K. foliaceum* is included in the list of bloom-forming species, very restricted in space and time, that occur every year in Northern Catalonia (Western Mediterranean, Spain) [8].

Different potentially toxic algal blooms occur in Ghar El Melh Lagoon (Tunisia), a region that should be subject to regular monitoring of HABs and their toxins. The lagoon, an important tourist resort due to its medicinal waters (balnearios), is very enclosed, but may contribute to the propagation of these HAB species into neighbouring coastal waters.

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S. Turki, N. Balti & C. Ben Salah, Institut National des Sciences et Technologies de la Mer, 2025 Salammbô, Tunisia.

Email: souad.turki@instm.rnrt.tn

• Italy

First record of *Prorocentrum lima* on Abruzzo Region coast, W Adriatic

Prorocentrum lima is a neritic and estuarine dinoflagellate (Dinophyceae) epiphytic on macroalgae and epibenthic on sediments or detritus. When found in the water column, it is generally in low abundance. The distribution ranges from tropical to temperate coastal waters. *P. lima* is a small to medium sized obovate cell with a central pyrenoid and a posterior nucleus. Each valve contains 50-80 regular marginal pores and about 60-100 evenly spaced pores on the valve surface.

Cells measure $36.61 \mu m$ in length and $25.19 \mu m$ in width for a length to width ratio of 1.45. There are 51 ± 1

regular marginal pores and 72 ± 1 small spaced pores per valve (average values) (Figs. 1a & 1b). The right valve has a shallow V-shape similar to a triangular excavation with a protruding flange (Figs. 1c & 1d). Finally, in figure 2a and 2b, the central pyrenoid can be seen. Cells were fixed with Lugol's solution and 0.4% formalin respectively [1].

P. lima first appeared on Italian Adriatic coasts was in 2006, in the Emilia Romagna Region (NW Adriatic) (Pompei pers.comm.) and Ancona [2];

Table 1. *P. lima* cell concentrations inside harbours during June, July and August 2007. Pump samples collected at 0.5 m below surface.

date	<i>P. lima</i> cell concentration (cells $\cdot L^{-1}$)	
	Pescara Harbour	Ortona Harbor
13 June 2007	-	472,230
09 July 2007	-	255,054
02 August 2007	-	50,650

it reached the western part of the Abruzzo Region in summer 2007. This species produces DSP toxins (Diarrhetic Shellfish Poisoning) that can contaminate filter-feeding shellfish and cause gastrointestinal illness in humans [3]. The complex of DSP toxins produced by *P. lima* includes okadaic acid (OA), dinophysistoxins (DTX-1,

Fig. 1. Scanning electron micrographs of *P. lima* strain isolated from Ortona harbour. (a) and (b) entire cell showing shape of theca, marginal pores and spaced pores, scale bar = 10 μm ; (c) periflagellar area in anterior part of cell. Scale bar = 10 μm ; (d) triangular excavation similar to a shallow V-shape with protruding flange. Scale bar = 5 μm .

DTX-2), prorocontrolide and fast acting toxin [4].

This is the first record of *P. lima* together with other toxic phytoplanktonic species collected these coasts. Sampling was carried out at six stations located 500 m and 3000 m offshore from Pescara, Ortona and Francavilla during June, July and August 2007. The stations were located using a GPS (Global Position System) Garmin GPS45. In addition, monthly samples were taken inside Pescara and Ortona harbours (Fig. 3). The harbours are potentially habitats for growth of toxic epibenthic species like *P. lima*, due to

the absence of water movements and stagnant environments.

Together with *P. lima*, we also observed other toxic and potentially toxic phytoplankton, including *Alexandrium minutum*, several toxic species of *Dinophysis*, potentially toxic *Pseudonitzschia*, *Gonyaulax spinifera*, *Lingulodinium polyedrum*, *Prorocentrum minimum*, and *Protoceratium reticulatum*.

At each station, one water sample was taken at 0.5 m by means of a pump, and net samples collected with a 10 μm mesh phytoplankton net. In the harbour areas, pump samples only were taken,

at 0.5 m.

Cell observations were made with a light microscope (ausJENA Telaval 3) at 400x and 1000x magnification, by the Utermöhl method using a volume of 50 ml, while net samples were counted reading the entire well using a volume of 2 ml.

P. lima first appeared on June 13th inside Ortona harbour, both over masses of *Ulva lactuca* and over the reef around the harbour perimeter. Its abundance in June was 4.7×10^5 cells L^{-1} at 0.5 m from the surface. This bloom was detected only inside the harbour area (table 1). The chemical-physical conditions were: pH 8.19, water temperature 24.1°C, salinity 36.28 psu, dissolved oxygen 7.7 mg L^{-1} .

Along the coast, *P. lima* was absent, but other toxic and potentially toxic species were present in the monthly samples. *Dinophysis caudata* was the most abundant at the six stations (2.0×10^3 cells L^{-1} in net sample; 40 cells L^{-1} in sample collected at 0.5 m), followed by *Lingulodinium polyedrum* (1.5×10^3 cells L^{-1} in net sample; 40 cells L^{-1} at 0.5 m), both at Ortona station 500 m from shore (called Ortona 500).

On July 9th and August 2nd *P. lima* concentrations inside Ortona harbour were 2.5×10^5 and 5.0×10^4 cells L^{-1} respectively (0.5 m sample). These values were lower than the previous month; this species has not been observed in Pescara harbour.

Chemical-physical parameters measured in July and August in Ortona harbour were respectively: pH 8.19 and 8.22 pH; temperature 25 and 22. 1°C, salinity 33.28 e 34.81 psu, dissolved oxygen 7.9 and 7.6 mg L^{-1} .

A periodical decrease in the *P. lima* cellular abundances inside Ortona harbour corresponded a monthly increase outside the harbor itself and specifically at 500 m from the coast of this station during July and August exactly. Its cellular concentrations were 1.0×10^3 and 5.0×10^2 cells L^{-1} in net sample along the water column respectively; 40 cells L^{-1} on July and 20 cells L^{-1} on August in samples collected at 0.5 m from the surface. These values are not considered an HAB phenomenon.

Chemical-physical parameters

Fig. 2. Light microscopy photographs of *P. lima* at 1000x magnification to show central pyrenoid. (a) cell fixed with Lugol's solution, scale bar = 10 μm . (b) cell fixed with 0.4% formalin, scale bar = 10 μm .

Fig. 3. sampling area.

Acknowledgements

To Francesco Mascioli, Stefano Teodori, Antonio Teodori, Nagore Sampedro and Sonia Quijano.

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C. Ingarao, G. Lanciani, C. Verri & T. Pagliani, Environmental Science Centre, Consorzio Mario Negri Sud Institute (CMNS), S. Maria Imbaro (CH), Italy.

Email: ingarao@negrisud.it

measured in this sampling point (Ortona 500) during these two last months were: 8.19 and 8.22 pH; 25 e 22° 1°C temperature; 33.28 e 34.81 psu salinity; 7.9 e 7.6 mg > L⁻¹ dissolved oxygen.

Maximum concentrations of other species these two months were *Prorocentrum minimum* (7.5 x 10³ cells L⁻¹ in net sample, 60 cells L⁻¹ in 0.5 m sample) in July at Pescara station at 500 m from shore; *Pseudo-nitzschia* (1.1 x 10⁶ cells L⁻¹ in net sample, 3.0 x 10⁵ cells L⁻¹ in 0.5 m sample) in July at Francavilla

station at 500 m from the shore; *Lingulodinium polyedrum* (1.4 x 10⁴ cells L⁻¹ in net sample, 1.4 x 10² cells L⁻¹ in 0.5 m sample), and *Dinophysis caudata* (4.5 x 10³ cells L⁻¹ in net sample, 60 cells L⁻¹ in 0.5 m sample) in August at Pescara station at 3000 m from shore.

Additional studies are needed to observe the periodical presence of *Prorocentrum lima* and other toxic and potentially toxic species along the coasts and inside harbors of Abruzzo region.

PICES HAB Activities

The North Pacific Marine Science Organization (PICES) Working Group 15 (WG 15) on *Ecology of Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs) in the North Pacific*, with Tatiana Orlova (Russia) and F.J.R (Max) Taylor (Canada) as co-chairs, began in October 1999 as the initial effort in HAB collaboration among PICES member countries (Canada, Japan, P.R. China, Republic of Korea, Russia and the United States). The terms of reference for this 3-year WG 15 were to:

1. Identify the various species involved, and the timing, frequency, and duration of harmful algal bloom events;
2. Develop a regional database of relevant observational parameters associated with bloom events, including maps, bibliography, data sets and

techniques, existing programs and expanded list of researchers in the area;

3. Investigate links between bloom events and environmental factors, trophic interactions and possible anthropogenic stress (e.g., eutrophication);

4. Assess the economic, health-related, and environmental impacts arising from harmful algal bloom events in order to improve the ability to predict the occurrence of these events and thus minimize their overall impacts;
5. Suggest areas where critical data are missing and where future research is necessary;
6. Facilitate regional collaborative research efforts at various levels to address these problems.

At the 2003 PICES Annual Meeting

C. Tomas preparing materials for the practical lab demonstration on harmful raphidophytes.

(PICES XII) in Seoul, Korea, it was proposed and accepted that the WG 15 activities be expanded, and that an on-going HAB efforts evolve into a HAB Section. The terms of reference of the HAB Section, co-chaired by Hak-Gyoon Kim (Korea) and Vera Trainer (U.S.A.) are to:

1. Develop and implement annual bloom reporting procedures that can be consistent with ICES procedures and therefore incorporated into the broader HAB dataset (HAEDAT). This step will be important in assessing impacts of HAB events and as a research tool to look at patterns that will facilitate efforts to develop predictive capabilities;

2. Create and document national reports of HAB incidents and research in order to inform Section members of new toxins, new developments, and new approaches. These reports target both toxin producing and non-toxic (but harmful) algal species will be included;

3. Raise awareness of current specific needs for scientific advice among PICES member countries by identifying topics of interest, and providing syntheses of the available scientific information on those selected topics.

Membership for the HAB Section can be found on the PICES website at www.pices.int/members/sections/HAB.aspx

The PICES HAB data efforts began during the Seoul meeting with a workshop on “*Harmonization of HAB data: Developing a North Pacific HAB data resource I*”. The following year at PICES XIII in Honolulu, U.S.A., the data workshop was titled, “*Harmonization of HAB data: Developing a North Pacific HAB data resource-II*”. At PICES XIV in Vladivostok, Russia, PICES collaborators Henrik Enevoldsen and Monica Lion from the IOC, gave a database demonstration, “*Toward the development of a joint IOC-ICES-PICES database*”. During that year, year 2000 HAB data for each PICES member country were entered into the Harmful Algal Event Database (HAEDAT), in a joint effort towards developing a global HAB database. The central tasks of the joint PICES-ICES HAEDAT were to:

1. Ascertain the data base process in PICES member countries;
2. Identify potential difficulties in delivery (e.g. confidentiality of data);
3. Assess the needs for the web-based data entry platform and;
4. Make any further modifications needed to represent the unique issues facing PICES member nations.

Selected HAB Section members and guest speakers, PICES XVI, Victoria, BC, Canada, Oct 07.

Another highlight of the PICES HAB Section is the ongoing annual sponsored workshops on selected harmful algae that began with the “*Review of selected harmful algae in the PICES region: Pseudo-nitzschia and Alexandrium*” (2005) then continued with *Dinophysis* and *Cochlodinium* (2006), *Heterosigma akashiwo* and other harmful raphidophytes (2007)”, with a plan for a workshop on *Karenia* and *Prorocentrum* at PICES XVII in Dalian, China. These workshops have featured summary presentations by invited experts and practical laboratory demonstrations in phytoplankton identification, toxin analysis, and other methods pertaining to the species of focus for that particular year.

The HAB Section within its parent committee on Marine Environmental Quality (MEQ) also has sponsored a number of special topic sessions on subjects of particular interest and pertinence to HAB researchers in the country hosting the Annual PICES Meetings. These topic sessions include: “*Natural and anthropogenic introduction of marine species*”, “*Harmful algal blooms in the PICES region: New trends and potential links with anthropogenic influences*”, “*The relative contribution of offshore/inshore HAB development and persistence in the PICES region*”. In Dalian, China at PICES XVII, the special topic session will be “*Environmental and anthropogenic influences of species succession towards HAB species dominance*”.

Finally, a 3-year PICES HAB

International project, sponsored by a grant from the Government of Japan, will help establish and implement monitoring programs in developing non-PICES nations. The sharing of such monitoring information will ensure the security of imported fisheries products, and will protect the coastal environment and ecosystems of Japan and other importing nations. HAB International will focus on assisting in the development of capabilities in Vietnam, Hong Kong, Malaysia, Philippines, Thailand, Mexico, Peru, Chile, but the project is not exclusive of other developing nations that are interested in participating. The primary aims for the pilot training workshops are to establish effective protocols, determine proper equipment, develop appropriate databases, and to design ideal teaching strategies. We seek the support of key national and local regional officials in developing nations, and an understanding of the regional operational structure and laboratory facilities in the countries suitable for hosting the workshops. Preliminary site visits in Year 1 of the project by the workshop organizers will be used to work with country representatives to design the framework for the workshops. We will begin the training workshops in Vietnam during Year 2 using established contacts at regional and local levels that members of the organizing committee have established.

PICES XVII will be held October 23-November 2, in Dalian, China.

V. Trainer, PICES-HAB Section Co-Chairman, NOAA, Seattle, WA, USA. Email: vera.l.trainer@noaa.gov

• India

A 'Red tide' caused by the diatom *Coscinodiscus* on the southwest coast of India

Fig. 1. *Coscinodiscus asteromphalus* var. *centralis* Cells x 40.

The International Council for Exploration of Seas defined phytoplankton blooms as "those, which are noticeable, particularly to the general public, directly or indirectly through their effects such as visible discoloration of the water, foam production, fish or invertebrate mortality or toxicity to humans". These are natural phenomena that occur in the sea under special hydrographical conditions, when the combined effects of grazing are less than biomass production due to growth of phytoplankton, and via advective processes. The accumulation of phytoplankton may be so dense that the water appears coloured red, green, brown, orange, etc. Numerous incidences of these blooms have been reported from many parts of the world ocean including Indian seas. The frequency of algal blooms in the recent past has been related to anthropogenic activities. Along the southwest coast of India, there are several reports of blooms caused by dinoflagellates, and

by the diatoms *Fragilaria* and *Hemidiscus*.

During the regular monitoring of Harmful Algal Blooms (HAB) in the Indian EEZ and estuaries, water discoloration due to a bloom of *Coscinodiscus asteromphalus* var. *centralis* was observed off Kodikkal-Calicut (11° 28.43' N, 75° 36.10' E) during the second week of August 2006. Though

dinoflagellate blooms have been reported every year during this period, this is the first time a monospecific bloom of this diatom causing red tide has been seen: the bloom spread into the estuary during high tide. In Mahe Estuary, the cell density was so high that the water colour was brownish red.

Surface water samples were collected in a clean plastic bucket about 1.5 km offshore. Temperature, salinity, pH, dissolved oxygen (DO) and nutrients (nitrate, phosphate and silicate) were estimated employing standard techniques. Water transparency was measured with a Secchi disc. Primary productivity, chlorophyll *a*, phytoplankton and zooplankton composition were also estimated. Phytoplankton samples were collected by filtering around 50 litres of surface water using 60 µm mesh bolting silk. The samples were examined microscopically and cell concentrations determined. The cell count of *Coscinodiscus* was 7×10^6 L⁻¹.

Along the southwest coast of India, red water is reported to occur between August and November, which marks the end of the upwelling period along this coast. Earlier workers have also observed that dinoflagellate blooms are preceded by rains and diatom maxima. Observations reviewed by Brongersma-Sanders [1] show that red tides occur in upwelling areas towards the end of upwelling

period and that diatom blooms precede dinoflagellate blooms in these regions. The period when red tides are generally reported coincides with the end of the upwelling season, when the weather is warmer with longer hours of sunshine than during the monsoon months. The hydrographic conditions measured during the bloom period were relatively low surface temperature (28°C) and relatively high salinity (34 ppt). NO₃-N was low (3.185 µmol L⁻¹) while the PO₄-P was high (2.185 µmol L⁻¹) resulting in a rather significant N: P ratio. The reactive silicate recorded (42.27 µmol L⁻¹), was very high for this period, which could be one of the reasons for the diatom bloom. Reduction in nitrate and increase in phosphate content could be a feature associated with the diatom bloom itself; similar increases in phosphate and decreases in nitrate have been reported during blooms by earlier workers. Increased photosynthetic activity resulted in high dissolved oxygen concentration (6.9 mg L⁻¹) in the surface waters. Primary production was 5.6 gC m⁻³ day⁻¹ and chlorophyll *a* (206.5 mg m⁻³) was several times higher than during normal productive periods. Zooplankton biomass was low (11.24 mg 1000m⁻³) and was comprised of a few species of copepods, copepodites and nauplii.

Acknowledgements

The authors are grateful to the Centre for Marine Living Resources and Ecology, Ministry of Earth Sciences, Govt. of India for financial assistance during this study.

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K.B. Padmakumar, M.G. Sanilkumar & A.V. Saramma, Dept. of Marine Biology, Cochin University, Kochi-16, Kerala, India. Email: kbpadmakumar@gmail.com.

N.R. Menon, Cochin University & Ministry of Earth Sciences, Kochi, Kerala, India.

Fig. 2. *C. asteromphalus* var. *centralis* Single cell x 200.

Happy New Year.

ISSHA

International Society for the Study of Harmful Algae

2008 promises to be an exciting and busy year for ISSHA

The General Assembly will convene during the 13th International Conference on Harmful Algae the first week in November 2008 in Hong Kong. Prior to the meeting members will have an opportunity to nominate their colleagues for awards as well as nominate candidates to serve as Officers (President, Vice-President, Secretary and Treasurer) and as Council members for the coming 3 year term.

The important dates to note are listed below but, first let me remind you that membership dues expire on 31 December. So check your membership status and renew your membership (via Nina Lundholm nlundholm@bi.ku.dk). You may not serve as a nominator for a candidate unless both you and the candidate are current ISSHA members. ISSHA dues are still only \$20 per year and \$10 per year for students. With the decreased value of the US dollar, this is quite a bargain.

On or by 3 July 2008 Nominations for Officers and Council Members.

Article 23. Elections.

I. Any member of the Society may nominate candidates, who shall be members of the Society, for the election as President, vice Presidents, Secretary, Treasurer or Members of Council.

II. All such nominations, with the name of a seconder and with written consent of the nominee to act if elected, shall be forwarded to the Secretary no later than four months before the General Assembly.

On or by 3 August 2008 Ballots Circulated to Membership

Article 23. Elections.

III. Voting shall be by written ballot. For this purpose, the Secretary shall circulate ballot forms to all members of the Society three months before the General Assembly. At the meeting, the ballot forms shall be opened and the count made by scrutineers appointed by

Council, and the results of the ballot shall be declared.

On or before 19 September 2008 Submit Agenda Items for General Assembly.

Article 17 General Assembly.

II. At the General Assembly, members of the Society present shall consider any business brought before them by the Council, or by any member (of which notice in writing has been given to the Secretary at least two weeks before distribution of the agenda).

On or by 3 October 2008 General Assembly Agenda.

Article 17 General Assembly.

I. Notice of the General Assembly shall be sent to each member by the Secretary at the earliest possible date (normally at least one year in advance), and the agenda of the meeting shall be sent out at least one month before the meeting and posted on the ISSHA website.

The agenda for the 2008 General Assembly will have suggested alterations to the Statutes to clarify ISSHA's business year and other minor changes.

ISSHA encourages its diverse membership and would like to have that diversity mirrored in the Committees as well. If you would like to serve on any of the following committees, please let one of the Officers or the Committee Chairs know of your interests.

I look forward to seeing you at the 13th Conference on Harmful Algae in Hong Kong and urge you to visit the ISSHA website at <http://www.issaha.org> for updates on the program and activities. Again, I wish each of you a prosperous and safe New Year.

*Pat Tester, President,
Email: pat.tester@noaa.gov*

Committee on Elections: Chair: K. Steidinger. Member: S. Bates.

Committee on Membership: Chair: P. Tester. Members: H.-G. Kim, B. Reguera, G. Hallegraeff & T. Smayda.

Committee on Finances: Chair: N. Lundholm. Members: D. Anderson, K. Steidinger, E. Granéli & Y. Fukuyo.

Committee on Conference Program: Chair: Ø. Moestrup. Members: D. Anderson, A. Cembella, B. Dale, G. Doucette & J. Lewis.

Committee on Achievement Awards: Chair: M. Montresor. Members: A. Cembella, H. Enevoldsen, B. Reguera & B. Dale.

Committee on Travel Awards: Chair: D. Anderson. Members: A. Cembella, H. Enevoldsen, B. Reguera, K. Steidinger, Y. Fukuyo & E. Granéli.

Committee on Publications: Chair: J. Lewis. Members: S. Bates, A. Cembella, B. Dale, G. Doucette, H. Enevoldsen, K. Steidinger, P. Tester & A. Zingone.

Ad hoc Committee on Special Projects: Co-chairs: H. Enevoldsen, P. Tester, A. Zingone.

Executive (2004-2007): Please note that all current Officers have agreed to serve until the 2008 election.

President: Pat Tester, Email: pat.tester@noaa.gov

Vice President: Gustaaf Hallegraeff, Email: hallegraeff@utas.edu.au

Vice President: Beatriz Reguera, Email: beatriz.reguera@vi.ieo.es

Secretary: Tracy Villareal, Email: tracy@utmsi.utexas.edu

Treasurer: Nina Lundholm, Email: nlundholm@bi.ku.dk

Past President: Karen Steidinger, Email: Karen.Steidinger@MyFWC.com

Council (2004-2007): D. Anderson (USA), B. Dale (Norway), G. Doucette (USA), Y. Fukuyo (Japan), E. Granéli (Sweden), H.-G. Kim (S. Korea), J. Lewis (UK), Ø. Moestrup (Denmark), M. Montresor (Italy), T. Smayda (USA) and A. Zingone (Italy).

Future events

FEBRUARY 2008

The ICES-IOC-SCOR Working Group on Implementation of GEOHAB in the Baltic

Gothenburg, Sweden, 27-29 February 2008.

The working group will meet to: review progress in implementation of the GEOHAB-BALTIC cooperative research plan, with reports from the projects in progress and reports from projects at planning stage; define processes and plan experiments that are needed for better parameterisation of dynamical HAB models; review the progress of incorporating the Baltic HAB list into the IOC Taxonomic Reference List of Toxic Plankton Algae; and discuss and report on the need of a Baltic HAB researcher network, in the light of the WG HABD comments on WGGIB performance.

OCTOBER 2008

Ciguatera workshop

Noumea, New Caledonia, 27-31 October 2008

The Organizing Committee is in the process of organizing the "Ciguatera and related biotoxins" Workshop. Dates were set in line with those of the 13th International Conference on Harmful Algae to be held in Hong Kong on 3-7 November 2008, as a satellite workshop and to allow participants to make the appropriate travel connections from Noumea to Hong Kong in good time.

The workshop will take place in the IRD and the Secretariat of the Pacific Community (SPC) symposium facilities, both based in Noumea and appropriately located next door to each other.

We would also like to kindly draw your attention to a special roundtable session on toxic marine cyanobacteria,

which will be organised on Tuesday evening, 28 October. The interest has come about as a result of our recent studies in New Caledonia and French Polynesia. This will enable valuable discussions with international scientists involved in this area and should provide the basis for new collaborative research and better use and allocation of funding from donors in the future. All those interested in this area of research are welcomed, and therefore please feel free to extend and share this announcement to your colleagues in this field of research.

For further information, please visit: <http://www.ird.nc/ciguatera> or ciguatera@noumea.ird.nc.

NOVEMBER 2008

13th International Conference on Harmful Algae 08

Hong Kong-China, 3-7 Nov 08.

ISSHA is pleased to announce the 13th Int. Conference on Harmful Algae. Supporting organizations include School of Science & Technology, the Open University of Hong Kong and the Association of Harmful Algal Bloom of South China Sea (AoHABSCS).

Further info: www.hab2008.hk.

Harmful Algae News

Previous issues of HAN and newsletters of the IOC HAB Programme can be downloaded at <http://ioc.unesco.org/hab/news.htm>

Requests for subscription

Subscription to HAN is made by sending a request with a complete address to Ms V. Bonnet: v.bonnet@unesco.org.

PHYCOTOXINS

You can also get news on HAB research and events at the Phycotoxins-list at the internet.

The address of this list is: phycotoxins@www.agr.ca

To join the list, send "subscribe phycotoxins" to: listserv@www.agr.ca

Archives are located at www.agr.ca/archives/phycotoxins.html

Harmful Algae News only exists if the Editor gets input from YOU!

Write the Editor NOW with news on your work, HAB events in your country or region, or any other matter you wish to share with HAB scientists and managers worldwide. Harmful Algae News has more than 2000 subscribers.

HARMFUL ALGAE NEWS

Compiled and edited by Tim Wyatt, Instituto de Investigaciones Marinas, CSIC, Eduardo Cabello 6, 36208 Vigo, Spain; Tel.: +34 986 23 19 30/23 19 73; Fax: +34 986 29 27 62; E-mail: twyatt@iim.csic.es and Mónica Lion, Centro Científico y de Comunicación sobre Algas Nocivas COI-IEO, Apdo. 1552, 36200 Vigo, Spain; Tel.: +34 986 49 21 11; Fax: +34 986 49 20 03; E-mail: monica.lion@vi.ieo.es

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Project Coordinator: Henrik Enevoldsen, IOC Science and Communication Centre on Harmful Algae, University of Copenhagen, Øster Farimagsgade 2D, DK-1353 Copenhagen K, Denmark Tel.: +45 33 13 44 46; Fax.: +45 33 13 44 47; E-mail: h.enevoldsen@unesco.org